

Eco-taxonomical studies on diatoms from the Godavari River, Nashik, Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT:

The study focused on evaluating the taxonomic details and geographic distribution of the periphytic genera *Achnanthes*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Gyrosigma*, *Cyclotella*, *Fragilaria*, *Pleurosigma*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Amphora*, *Cymbella*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Stauroneis*, *Neidium* and *Caloneis* in various parts of Godavari River. Over the course of three years from January 2022 to December 2024, samples were gathered from multiple sites around the dam. Findings include the identification of 01 species of *Achnanthes*, *Caloneis*, *Amphora*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Stauroneis*, *Neidium*, *Pleurosigm*, *Anomoeoneis* and *Cyclotella*, 09 species of *Navicula*, 08 species of *Pinnularia*, 05 species of *Gyrosigma*, 03 species of *Fragilaria* and *Cymbella*, all of which were documented for the first time in this location. The highest diversity of these species was observed during the winter, followed by the monsoon and summer seasons. The physicochemical parameters of the Godavari River water were found to be highly conducive for the growth of these taxa. This research underscores the potential of using *Achnanthes*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Gyrosigma*, *Cyclotella*, *Fragilaria*, *Pleurosigma*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Amphora*, *Cymbella*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Stauroneis*, *Neidium* and *Caloneis* as biological indicators in freshwater ecosystems.

Keyword: - Diatoms, Bacillariophyceae, Godavari River, Nashik district, Maharashtra.

INTRODUCTION:

A preliminary survey of algae in the Godavari River was conducted at various sites during the years 2022–2024. The study revealed the presence of numerous planktonic algae in the water body. Several taxa of freshwater algae were recorded from different locations along the river. The dominant species observed at certain sites during the winter season

included *Achnanthes*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Gyrosigma*, *Cyclotella*, *Fragilaria*, *Pleurosigma*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Amphora*, *Cymbella*, *Neidium*, and *Caloneis*.

The present work represents a significant systematic study on the algal diversity of the Godavari River. This investigation is an outcome of broader biodiversity studies focused on the freshwater algae of the region and contributes to our understanding of the algal flora in this area. Accordingly, the study of the aquatic vegetation was undertaken during the years 2022–2024.

During the study, a large number of phytoplankton's like *Achnanthes*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Gyrosigma*, *Cyclotella*, *Fragilaria*, *Pleurosigma*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Amphora*, *Cymbella*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Stauroneis*, *Neidium* and *Caloneis* were observed. However, the algal flora of Godavari River has not been studied so far and this is the first report. For the present study, different locations of the Godavari River water body were selected. The water samples from each locality were collected once in a month in the morning between 8.00 a.m. to 11.00 a.m. The collections were made for 3 years during 2022-2024, during the months of November to March. For phytoplankton analysis, water samples were collected by plankton net, as per the method adopted by Narkhede (2006). 20 liters of surface water was collected (by standing in the back water of dam at about 100-120 cm depth) by dipping a jug and filtered through the plankton net and was collected in 1 lit. wide mouth bottle, 30 ml of water sample was preserved in 4% formalin. The morphological studies of specimens were done by using Olympus Research Microscope and Labomed Microscope and the photographs were taken using Kodak EazyShare cx 7330 cameras. Identification of taxa was done using Fritsch (1935), Patel and George (1977), Philipose (1967), Prescott (1951), Rath and Adhikari (2005) and other relevant literature.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Algal samples from each site were collected once a month in the morning, between 8:00 a.m. and 10:00 a.m., during the years 2022 to 2024. Samples were collected in 100 ml capacity bottles and transported to the laboratory. For preservation and further taxonomic investigation, the samples were transferred to 20 ml capacity bottles containing 4% formalin. For the collection of macroalgae, 1000 ml capacity bottles were used, and the preservation method was the same as described above. Phytoplankton samples were collected using a plankton net, following the method described by Narkhede (2006). Twenty liters of surface water from the Godavari River (at a depth of approximately 100–120 cm) were collected by

dipping a jug about 3 cm below the surface. The collected water was filtered through the plankton net, and the concentrate was stored in a 1-liter wide-mouth bottle. In the laboratory, 20 ml of the sample was preserved in 4% formalin, as previously described.

1. *A. inflata* (Kuetz.) Grun. f. *vidarbhensis* Sarode et Kamat (Pl. 1, Fig.1)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 55, pl 5, f 115

Valves 89-95.5 μ long; 16-16.6 μ broad, linear trigibbous with broadly cuneate rounded ends; raphe valve with thin and straight raphe, axial area fairly broad, linear, central area stauroid, reaching the margins; striae 9-10 in 10 μ , radial and punctate; rapheless valve with unilateral, narrow pseudoraphe; central area absent; striae 9 in 10 μ , coarsely punctate, curved at the ends.

2. *N. cryptocephala* Kuetz. (Pl. 1, Fig.2)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 106, pl 12, f 254

Valves 22-35.5 μ long 8.5-9.2 μ broad, lanceolate with produced, rounded ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow; central area slightly extended transversely, small; striae 10-12 in 10 μ , radial in the middle and slightly convergent at the ends.

3. *Navicula cryptocephala* kuetz. *V. exilis* Grun. (Pl. 1, F. 3)

Cleve-euler, 1953, P.154, F. 813 c-e, k.

Valves 18.7-21.8 4 μ m long, 4.8-5.5 μ m broad, small, raphe thin and straight, axial area very narrow; central area roundish; striae 20-22 in 10 μ m very fine, radial at middle and convergent at the ends; central straiie shorter.

4. *N. cuspidata* Kuetz. v. *ambigua* (Ehr.) Cleve f. *diminuta*. A.Cl. (Pl. 1, Fig. 4)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 108, pl 12, f 261

Valves 60-85 μ long, 16.1-20.5 μ broad, broadly lanceolate with constricted, rounded ends; raphe thin and straight with unilaterally bent central pores; axial area narrow, transverse striae 14-16 in 10 μ , longitudinal striae 20-22 in 10 μ , fine.

5. *N. dicephala* (Ehr.) W. Smith v. *sphaerophora* A. Cl. (Pl. 1, Fig. 5)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 110, pl 13, f 268

Valves 20-25 μ long, 7-8 μ broad, linear or linear elliptical with constricted, capitate, rounded ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area fairly large, somewhat roundish, striae 14-15 in 10 μ , radial throughout and curved.

6. *N. radiosa* Kuetz v. *tenella* Hustedt. (Pl. 1, Fig. 6)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 120, pl 14, f 306

Valves 27.5-34 μ long, 5.6-6.5 μ broad, narrowly lanceolate and gradually tapering to somewhat acutely rounded ends, raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, central area large, rounded, striae 14-16 in 10 μ , radial in the middle.

7. *N. feverborni* (Feverb.) Hustedt (Pl. 1, Fig. 7)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 111, pl 13, f 271

Valves 35.5-41 μ long; 6.5-7.5 μ broad, linear lanceolate with broadly rounded ends; raphe thin and straight, axial area very narrow; central area small, unilateral, striae 14 in 10 μ , strong and strongly radial.

8. *N. reinhardtii* Grun. f. *gracilior* Grun. (Pl. 1, Fig. 8)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 121, pl 14, f 307

Valves 54.9-64 μ long, 9-12 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate with broadly rounded ends, raphe somewhat thick and straight with distinct central pores; axial area narrow; central area large, striae 9-10 in 10 μ , radial throughout.

9. *N. rhynchocephala* Kuetz. (Pl. 1, F. 9).

Hustedt 1930, P.-296, F.-501.

Valves 50.24 μ mm long, 12.02 μ mm broad, oblong, slender, with slightly dilated capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area rounded, somewhat rhombic, striae 14-16 in 10 μ mm, denser towards the ends - radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

10. *Navicula viridula* kuetz.v. *vidarbhensis* Sarode et. Kamat. (Pl. 1, F. 10).

Sarode and kamat 1983, P.-311, Pl. 10, F.-114.

Valves 96 μ mm long, 26 μ mm broad, lanceolate with broad, slightly rostrate and capitate ends; raphe thin, enclosed in between siliceous ribs - central pores somewhat unilaterally inclined and terminal fissures curved pores somewhat unilaterally inclined and terminal fissures curved; axial area narrow; central area sub orbicular; striae 9-10 in 10 μ mm, strong, lineate, radial in the middle and slightly convergent at the ends.

11. *Pinnularia acrosphaeria* (Breb.) W.Smith (Pl.1, Fig. 11)

Sarode and Kamat 1984, p 133, pl 15, f 340.

Valves 36.5 μ long, 6.5 μ broad, linear, slightly inflated in the middle and at the ends; raphe thin and straight with closely set, axial area very wide with irregularly disposed punctate; striae 12-14 in 10 μ , very slightly radial.

12. *P. acrosphaeria* (Breb.) W. Smith f. *undulata* Cleve. (Pl. 1, Fig. 12)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 133-134, pl 15, f 341

Valves 56.5-72 μ long, 10-11.5 μ broad, linear, inflated in the middle with broadly rounded ends; raphe thin and straight with closely set, axial area very wide, with irregularly disposed punctate; central area not prominent; striae 12-14 in 10 μ slightly radial in the middle.

13. *P. brevicostata* Cleve.v. *indica* Gandhi (Pl. 1, Fig. 13)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 138, pl 15, f 357

Valves 87.5-97 μ long, 19.5-21 μ broad, linear elliptical with rounded ends; raphe thick with central pores unilaterally bent, axial area wide, lanceolate; striae 6 in 10 μ , very coarse.

14. *P. divergens* w. *smith* v. *laticeps* Frengu. (Pl. 1, F. 14)

Skuja, 1949, P.169, Pl.34, F. 21, 27

Valves 48.5-55 μ m long, 11.3-11.7 μ m broad, linear lanceolate with constricted, slightly produced feebly capitate ends; raphe, axial area, central area as in the type; striae 10-12 in 10 μ m, strongly-radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

15. *P. dolosa* Gandhi (Pl. 1, Fig. 15)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 141, pl 16, f 367

Valves 79.2-90 μ long, 14.4-14.9 μ broad, linear, tumid in the middle with slightly swollen broadly rounded ends; raphe formed in the hyaline zone, central pores closely set and unilaterally bent, terminal fissures curved; axial area wide, with fine irregularly disposed punctate; central area slightly unilaterally dilated; striae 9-11 in 10 μ , thick, slightly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

16. *P. legumen* Ehr. v. *florentina* (Grun.) Cleve. (Pl. 1, Fig. 16)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 145-146, pl 17, f 383

Valves 64.2-75 μ long, 12.7-13 μ broad, linear lanceolate with triundulate margins and constricted, slightly produced, capitate ends; raphe thick somewhat undulated; axial area wide, linear; central area large, striae 8-11 in 10 μ , thick strongly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

17. *P. marathwadensis* Sarode and Kamat (Pl. 1, Fig. 17)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 148, pl 19, f 426

Valves 95-104 μ long, 12.6-13 μ broad, linear, slightly gibbous in the middle with broadly rounded ends; raphe thick, with thick unilaterally bent central pores and slightly curved semicircular terminal fissures; axial area wide, about 1/5-1/4 the breadth of the valve;

central area large, rhomboid, narrowly reaching the margins; striae 10-14 in 10 μ , radial and slightly curved in the middle and convergent at the ends.

18. *P. psudoluculenta* Gandhi (Pl. 1, Fig. 18)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 152, pl 18, f 404

Valves 126-137 μ long, 17.5-18 μ broad, narrowly linear with concave margins in between the middle and the ends with gradually swollen broadly rounded ends; raphe thick, complex with central pores unilaterally bent and terminal fissures obliquely curved; axial area about 1/3 the breadth of the valve, linear lanceolate; central area quadrate; striae 7-8 in 10 μ , thick, slightly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends with distinct narrow bands.

19. *Gyrosigma acuminatum* (Kuetz.) Rabh. (Pl. 1, Fig. 19)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 67, pl 7, f 145

Frustules solitary; valves 99-106.5 μ long, 10-12.8 μ broad, sigmoid, lanceolate in outline, gradually tapering from the middle towards the ends; ends broadly rounded; raphe sigmoid and central; axial area narrow; central area small and elliptical; striae 18 in 10 μ ; transverse and longitudinal striae at equal distances from one another.

20. *Gyrosigma bhusawalensis sarode and Kamat.* (Pl. 1, F. 20)

Sarode and kamat, 1984, P.67, Pl.7, F.153.

Values 123.7 μ m long, 22.6 μ m broad, slightly sigmoid, linear attenuated towards the poles with obliquely rounded ends; raphe central and sigmoid; axial area very narrow; central area small, elliptical; transverse striae 14 in 10 μ m longitudinal striae 17 in 10 μ m distinct.

21. *G. khandeshensis* Sarode and Kamat (Pl. 1, Fig. 21)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 67, pl 17, f 154

Frustules free floating, solitary; valves 91-100.8 μ long, 13.6-18 μ broad, slightly sigmoid, linear lanceolate with broadly rounded ends; raphe central, slightly sigmoid, axial area narrow; central area small and elliptical; transverse striae 22-24 in 10 μ , slightly radial, fine but distinct; longitudinal striae 18-20 in 10 μ , fine.

22. *G. kuetzigii* (Grun.) Cleve (Pl. 1, Fig.22)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 68, pl 7, f 149

Valves 85.4-93 μ long, 12.8-14.4 μ broad, slightly sigmoid, lanceolate with rounded ends; raphe in the centre, slightly sigmoid; axial area narrow, linear, central area small; transverse striae 24 in 10 μ , coarse; longitudinal striae 26 in 10 μ , fine.

23. *Gyrosigma spencerii* (w.smith) cleve v. *nodiferu'm* (Grun.) A.c1. (Pl. 1, F. 23)

Cleve-Euler, 1952, P.14, F.1344d.

Values 50.2-64µm long, 10-12.8µm broad, slightly sigmoid, ends rounded raphe central, sigmoid, central, area, elliptical, transverse striae 18-20 in 10µm, radial; longitudinal striae 24-26 in 10µm, fine.

24. *Cyclotella glomerata* Bachmann. (Pl. 2, F. 24).

Hustedt, 1930, P.-105, F-18.

Frustules small, in loose chains - rectangular in girdle view; valves discoid 9.5µm in diameter, central field smooth with 6-7 small radial striae or dots in a ring, striae 8-10 striae in 10 µm. In present diatoms 11 µm diameter.

25. *Fragilaria intermedia* Grun. (Pl. 2, F. 25)

Hustedt, 1930, P.139, F130.

Frustules united together to form a long band - linear rectangular in the girdle view; values 75-92.3µm long, 6-7µm broad, linear with parallel margins; ends gradually tapering and rounded, arial area narrow, striae 10-12 in 10µm. In present diatoms 91.5 µm in long.

26. *Fragilaria Virescens* Ralf. (Pl. 2, F. 26)

Hustedt, 1930, P.-142, F.-144.

Frustules attached together to form chains - broadly linear valves 64.24µm long, 8.7µm broad, pseudoraphe striae marginal thin; central area unilateral; values elliptic, striae 12-19 in 10µm.

27. *Fragilaria virescens* Ralfs v. *capitata* Krasske (Pl. 2, F. 27)

Hustedt, 1930, P.-142, F.-145.

Valves 113.88µm long, 7.3µm broad, linear with capitate ends; pseudoraphe narrower, transverse striae fine 12-19 in 10µm; central area absent; axial area absent.

28. *Pleurosigma salinarum* Grun. (Pl. 2, F. 28)

Hustedt, 1930, P 228, F. 344.

Valves 74.5-135µm long, 12.4-14µm broad, linear, lanceolate, sharply rounded at the poles - transverse striae about 25 in 10µm, oblique striae about 30 in 10µm very conspicuous.

29. *Stauroneis anceps* Ehr.v. *hyaline* Brun. et perag. (Pl. 2, F. 29)

Hustedt, 1930, P. 256, F. 408.

Valves 53.1-61µm long, 10-10.8µm broad, subelliptical lanceolate with produced, feebly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight, central pores distinct and terminal fissures very slightly curved; central area large, striae about 30 in 10µm, radial and very finely punctate.

30. *Anomoeoneis lanceolata* Gandhi (Pl. 2, F. 30).

Gandhi, 1959 d, P.134, F.9, 10

Valves 48-62µm long, 14.16µm broad, somewhat broadly lanceolate, robust with rostrates; raphe thin and straight with prominent central pores and curved terminal fissures; axial area narrow, linear; central area large, unilateral, striae 18-20 in 10µm slightly radial, coarsely punctate.

31. *Amphora ovalis* Kuetz v. *libyca* (Ehr.) Cleve. (Pl. 2, F. 31)

Cleve-Euler 1953, P.-90, F.-666 a, b.

Frustules linear elliptical with truncate ends in the girdle view; valves 45.2-57.5µm long, 8.10µm broad, lunate, convex on the dorsal side, concave on the ventral side with a slight median indentation; ends rounded; raphe thin arcuate with middle part curved upwards and terminal fissures ventrally directed; axial area very narrow; central area large, rectangular on dorsal side bounded by striae 12-14 in 10µm, fairly radial throughout, coarse and traversed by 3-4 irregular longitudinal lines. Short on the ventral side, radial in the middle and convergent at the ends. In present diatoms 45.4 µm long, 10 µm broad.

32. *Cymbella aspera* (Ehr.) Cleve. (Pl. 2, F. 32)

Hustedt, 1930, P. 365, F. 680

Valves 83-160µm long, 22-32µm broad, asymmetrical with strongly convex dorsal and straight or slightly convex ventral side; ends obtusely rounded; raphe thick, arcuate, slightly excentric with large, ventrally bent central pores and dorsally directed terminal fissures; axial area moderate, linear; central area slightly formed, rounded with an arcuate marking on the dorsal side; striae 8-10 in 10µm, radial, clear and coarsely punctate. In present diatoms 85 µm long and 25 µm broad.

33. *Cymbella laevis* Naeg. (Pl. 2, F. 33)

Hustedt, 1930, P-353, F-643

Valves 22µm long, 8µm broad, nearly lanceolate, dorsal margin convex and ventral margin nearly straight or with a slight median inflation; ends rounded; raphe slightly thick, almost straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area small; striae 12-14 in 10µm, lineate, radiate, more widely set on the dorsal side.

34. *Cymbella tumida* (Breb.) V.H. f. *ventricosa* Gandhi. (Pl. 2, F. 34)

Gandhi, 1964, P. 371, F. 68.

Valves 52-88µm long, 14-19.5µm broad, asymmetrical, and curved, broadly naviculoid, with rostrate poles - dorsal margin convex and ventral margin straight or slightly convex with median expansion; raphe excentric; axial area narrow; central area large,

rounded with ventrally placed prominent dot; striae 9-10 on 10 μ m radial and punctate. In present Diatoms 57 μ m and 14.2 μ m broad.

35. *A. sculpta* (Ehr.) Cleve (Pl. 2, Fig. 35)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 98, pl 11, f 236

Valves 28.5-57.6 μ long, 11.5-14.4 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate, robust with constricted rostrate ends; raphe thin and straight with central pores unilaterally bent and terminal fissures slightly curved, axial area narrow, linear; central area large, unilaterally expanded with very fine indistinct punctae, irregularly disposed; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , radial, coarsely punctate, crossed by many hyaline longitudinal irregular spaces.

36. *Stauroneis kirtikarii* Sarode and Kamat (Pl. 2, Fig. 36)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 91, pl 11, f 230

Valves 32.5-38.4 μ long, 8.1-10 μ broad, elliptic to linear elliptic with broadly rostrate, very slightly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight with distinct central pores; axial area narrow, central area large, stauroid, narrowed towards the margins; striae 22-24 in 10 μ , very fine and finely punctate.

37. *Neidium affine* (Ehr.) Cleve v. *amphirhynchus* (Ehr.) Cleve f. *truncatula* **Gonzalves** et Gandhi (Pl. 2, Fig.37)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 78, pl 9, f 179

Cells usually solitary and free floating, rectangular in girdle view, without intercalary bands, valves 39-50 μ long, 10-12 μ broad, linear with almost parallel margins, suddenly contracted towards the ends and produced into broadly truncate poles, raphe thin and straight, central pores bent in opposite directions and terminal fissures narrowly bifurcated; axial area narrow; central area small and rhomboid; striae 20-22 in 10 μ , fine but clearly punctate, crossed by a hyaline furrow near the margins.

38. *Caloneis permagna* (Bail.) Cleve (Pl. 2, Fig. 38)

Sarode and Kamat, 1984, p 72, pl 8, f 164

Frustules large and robust; valves 70-132 μ long, 27.4-41 μ broad, rhombic lanceolate with somewhat produced, broadly rounded ends; raphe thick and straight; central pores large, unilaterally bent, terminal fissures broadly curved and clear; axial area large, moderately lanceolate; central area large, circular and somewhat unilateral; striae 13-14 in 10 μ , radial in the middle and convergent at the ends; crossed by two longitudinal lines slightly away from the margin.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Recent research indicates that the diatom community in the Godavari River, particularly within the Nashik district, is both abundant and diverse. Among the 38 species identified, the genus *Navicula* is the most prevalent, comprising 9 species. Additionally, single species were recorded from genera such as *Achnanthes*, *Caloneis*, *Amphora*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Neidium*, *Pleurosigma*, and *Cyclotella*. Other significant genera include *Pinnularia* (8 species), *Gyrosigma* (5 species), and *Fragilaria* and *Cymbella* (3 species each).

Regular seasonal surveys are essential for comprehensive documentation of these diatom communities. However, rapid urbanization and environmental degradation are contributing to a swift decline in freshwater habitats within the region. This underscores the urgent need for conservation efforts to protect these ecosystems and the algal communities they support.

Raising awareness about the importance of preserving these freshwater habitats is critical, as they play a vital role in maintaining ecological balance. Due to their high species diversity, these habitats serve as effective indicators for monitoring the ecological health of the region. Furthermore, comprehensive limnological studies are recommended to strengthen the utility of these ecosystems in ecological monitoring and conservation planning.

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PLATE:-1

Fig. 1. *Achnanthes inflata* f. *vidarbhensis* 2. *Navicula cryptocephala* 3. *N. cryptocephala* V. *exilis* 4. *N. cuspidata* v. *ambigua* f. *diminuta* 5. *N. dicephala* v. *sphaerophora* 6. *N. radiosa* v. *tenella* 7. *N. feverborni* 8. *N. reinhardtii* f. *gracilior* 9. *N. rhynchocephala* 10. *N. viridula* v. *vidarbhensis* 11. *Pinnularia acrosphaeria* 12. *P. acrosphaeria* f. *undulata* 13. *P. brevicostata* v. *Indica* 14. *P. divergens* v. *laticeps* 15. *P. dolosa* 16. *P. legumen* v. *florentina* 17. *P. mahathwadensis* 18. *P. pseudoluculenta* 19. *Gyrosigma acuminatum* 20. *G. bhusawalensis* 21. *G. khandeshensis* 22. *G. kuetzigii* 23. *G. spencerii* v. *nodiferum*

PLATE:-2

Fig. 24. *Cyclotella glomerata* 25. *Fragilaria intermedia* 26. *F. Virescens* 27. *F. virescens* v. *capitata* 28. *Pleurosigma salinarum* 29. *Stausroneis anceps* v. *hyaline* 30. *Anomoeoneis lanceolata* 31. *Amphora ovalis* v. *libyca* 32. *Cymbella aspera* 33. *C. laevis* 34. *C. tumida* 35. *Anomoeoneis sculpta* 36. *Stauroneis kirtikarii* 37. *Neidium affix.* v. *amphirhynchus* f. *truncatula* f. *ventricosa* 38. *Caloneis permagna*